

**LETTERS AGAINST CASSANDRA RIOS: DIALOGUES BETWEEN
THE HISTORY OF THE PRESENT TIME, CENSORSHIP AND GENRE** DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7178510**Hevila Maria Sousa Santos**

Master's student in Atlantic History and Social Formations at the Postgraduate Program in History at the Federal University of Maranhão, PPGHIS/UFMA. Email: hevilamaria.sousa@gmail.com. Advisor: Prof. Dr. John Baptist Bitencourt.

Abstract: Studying the theoretical relationships between History and Literature gives us the opportunity to move History in other scopes, both for the theoretical debate that is inserted, and for the opportunity to revisit the past from literary sources. The São Paulo writer Cassandra Rios (1932-2002), known for writing lesbian and erotic novels, was censored during the entire civil-military regime that was in force in Brazil between 1964 and 1985. According to the regime, her works were inadequate for the Brazilian population, as it offended the moral values and good customs that were sought to preserve the Brazilian people. This discourse was not created by the military in power, nor was it restricted to the Brazilian reality reserved for that period. On the contrary, the censorship of sexualities considered deviant gained strength since decades before the coup of 64. And the discourse of preserving the good customs of the population has its roots in the heart of the Cold War, which favored, through anti-communist propaganda, the birth of the relationship between homosexuality, promiscuity and danger to the nation. Based on the readings of Michel de Certeau and Carlos Fico, we brought two letters written by civilians and addressed to the Minister of Justice Armando Falcão, against Cassandra Rios, imbued with these values and discourses that must be read from the point of view of time, but also of the permanence of discourses that are still reproduced.

Keywords: Cassandra Rios. Censorship. Genre. History. Literature.

In 1964, the years of the military regime began in Brazil, where a dictatorship was established through a coup d'état. The military and its supporters put their economic, social and ideological plans into practice. It was nothing new. There was in those years in South America a dense fog that weighed down the air, suffocating and destabilizing democratic governments: other coups followed in neighboring countries such as Argentina (1976) , Chile (1974) and Uruguay (1973) and even before Brazil, Paraguay has lived under this spectrum since 1954.

Although there are particularities in the operationalization of dictatorships in these countries, there are profound similarities between them when we compare the contexts that each one lived before, during and after the dictatorships. The violence that the police and politics

practiced on the resistance varied in *modus operandi* from the perspective of each place. But, in general, to sustain the regime, it was necessary to inculcate its purposes in the population. Therefore, for us to get to the letters against Cassandra Rios, it is necessary to write about the main objective of the military when they took power.

The world lived under the context of a complex and multifaceted conflict born from the Second World War, which defined international relations for almost half a century, the Cold War (MCMAHON, 2012). A war between the powers of the United States and the Soviet Union that disputed political-economic influence among other countries, provoking armed conflicts on other continents, such as the Korean War (1950-1953) and Vietnam (1955-1975) in Asia; and the Angolan Civil War (1975-2002) in Africa. The threat of governments that obeyed the communist doctrines of the Soviet Union in South America, caused the United States to interfere in the governments of the region, including Brazil.

The anti-communist campaign undertaken by the Brazilian military and businessmen sponsored by the United States was dedicated to inculcating untruths and myths in order to create aversion of the population towards the government of the Soviet Union and its allied countries. Interestingly, this was not restricted to the economic plan, nor to the political sphere, but also to social and private life, incorporating conservative parameters sheltered in Judeo-Christian precepts, reaching sexualities.

In view of this, when we refer to *the civil-military dictatorship* , we want to emphasize that neither the coup nor the consequent regime sustained itself, there was a part of the civil community that supported the maintenance of the regime from beginning to end. However, we cannot say that this is the most common term among historians, some such as Monica Piccolo and Mariana da Sulidade (2015) use the term *military-business dictatorship* to refer to this period of national history. Emphasizing that the coup and its aftermath were maintained through alliances between the military and businessmen and, thus, continued until 1985 ².

Given the above, we explore the anti-communist campaign of that period under the bias of censorship, which affected the press and other national cultural manifestations such as literature, music, cinema, artists and writers. Thus, we locate Cassandra Rios, the primary object of our research, as a writer who lived and published during that nebulous period of our history, where the density of fog reached her artistic production and sexualities considered deviant and some marks of this recent past perpetuate until today.

²As for the end of the civil-military dictatorship, there is also no consensus: some historians define it when a civilian assumed the Presidency of the Republic through indirect election, in 1985. Others prefer to point out it when the Citizen Constitution was promulgated, in 1988.

Cassandra Rios, pseudonym of Odete Rios (1932-2002), was a writer from São Paulo known for her boldness in writing about female homosexuality and for her extensive production. Her first novel was *Volúpia do Pecado*, written in 1948, when the author was only 16 years old. In this telenovela, two young women relate naturally and discover love and sexual pleasure together. His later novels followed suit. It is noteworthy, however, that she is not among the great names of national literature, nor has she had an award-winning book. On the contrary, Rios' books were considered "marginal"³ by critics, due to their simple writing, language that reproduced the style of popular writings and serial novels (SANTOS, 2003), whose characters are categorized as shallow, in narratives with nuances. dramatic and predictable endings. However, such categorization does not correspond to the reception given by the books of the aforementioned author, since, even censored by the dictatorial regime in Brazil, she continued to produce.

In 1970, as stated in the report of the National Truth Commission, released in 2014, of its 36 published works, 33 were banned. According to articles published in the newspapers O Globo (NOS ANOS..., 2013) and Folha de São Paulo (CORTECERTU, 2018), the author in question was the first Brazilian woman to reach the mark of one million books sold. In this sense, based on the assumption that homosexuality normalized a stereotype set apart from the "regular" Brazilian society, it is interesting to see that the object of this analysis was consolidated, at the time, as a spokesperson for the LGBTQIA+ minority⁴.

In this way, dictatorships in South America can be thought of as linked to other "traumatic events", as the historian Carlos Fico (2012) writes, characteristic of the 20th century, so we can place it in the context of theoretical debates on the History of Present Time. Thus, when looking for elements that made us think about this approach, we chose Michel de Certeau and François Dosse as the main theorists in this essay, due to their contributions regarding the historiographical operation and dialogues with the issue of the History of the Present Time. We

³According to Oliveira (2011), the term "marginal" involves complexities that concern a pattern of aesthetic, social and political conceptions and has a specific application in contemporary Brazilian literature from an aesthetic-cultural point of view.

⁴According to Facchini and França (2009), from the 1990s onwards, the homosexual movement grew and became politically organized in Brazil, in favor of their rights and greater representation. In 1993, it appeared as the Gay and Lesbian Movement (MGL); two years later, the acronym GLT appeared, which stands for Gays, Lesbians and Transvestites; in 1999, the movement began to identify itself as Gays, Lesbians, Bisexuals and Transgenders (GLBT), passing through the GLTB or LGBT variants, the latter being the best known and including people who identify as gay, lesbian, bisexual, transvestite, transsexuals and transgender people. The acronym GLS, on the other hand, was also created in the first half of the 1990s and intended to define a market segment aimed at "gay and lesbian" consumers, but which had the potential to include "heterosexual" consumers, called "sympathizers". Currently, in respect of gender diversity, the acronym LGBTQIA+ has become more common and encompasses lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transsexuals, queer, intersex and + (other groups and variations of sexuality and gender).

therefore take on the challenge of undertaking a discussion of the documents that follow this approach, even if it is an initial one for us.

Historiography, which is part of the historian's practice, is a discourse that is associated with something beyond it. According to Certeau, the historiographical discourse starts from an object, a document, lost and dead, since it treats death as a means of knowledge. Thus, according to Oriani (2017), it is possible to observe the space between the practice and its report, that is, historiography, since the historian operates on the document in the light of his interests and method preferences, which implies, in the existence of “voids” in the writing of history and must be observed from the perspective of the current or approach employed.

In this orientation, one of the particularities of the History of the Present Time is the tension of contemporaries for the search for truth, in other words, the probability of the past being confronted by the testimonies of those who experienced the events (FICO, 2012). According to Fico, the central characteristic of the History of the Present Time is part of its implication with politics, as it permeates the circumstance of being interposed in the same temporality, groping for its permanences, sheltered in a contemporary dimension, especially in the perception that events have this *endless* character .

The difficulties of undertaking an investigation in the History of the Present Time must be faced with the understanding that it is essential to provide a plausible explanatory basis for recent events (PADROS, 2009). That is, starting from an analytical basis of the sources to apprehend history as a process. Dosse explains that the notion of “present time” is a means of revisiting the certainties and uncertainties of the past, taking into account that “the temporal distance that separates us from the past is transformed, because until then considered a disadvantage, it becomes a sedimentation of successive layers of meaning” (DOSSE, 2012, p.11), without falling into the temptations of anachronisms.

Thus, the discussion that we elaborate below is the result of the effort to analyze the documents not only in the light of the History of the Present Time, but also to relate the repressive archives, their speeches and arguments regarding the work of Cassandra Rios from a perspective of the debate of genre. Once homosexuality was considered as an attack on the morals and good customs of Brazilian society. Therefore, the development of facts from this perspective demands the relationship of events with the historical process, but what makes censorship of moral themes an instrument of state police power?

Anti-communism and defense of morals and good customs

Historian Robert Darnton (2016) writes that the definition of censorship is quite broad, but that to generalize it to any control effort is to risk trivializing it. However, we can point out that censorship was present in different states and with specific objectives depending on the time-space to be studied. In our country, censorship was a legitimate instrument usual in sectors of civil society, a commitment to what was considered useful to the ideals of the Christian family that the State defended (SETEMY, 2018).

Censorship is a common feature among authoritarian regimes, so suppressing freedom of expression is a mechanism of domination by limiting or eliminating dissenting manifestations (REIMÃO, 2014), but it is also not the only means. Allied to political police, espionage and political propaganda, censorship is yet another tool for restricting freedom. Its origin in Brazil, as indicated by Fico (2001), did not take place specifically to work during the period of the Military Dictatorship; because it had already been used in the Estado Novo and, therefore, was only updated.

Soares states that, in Brazil, freedom of the press was guaranteed to Brazilians by Dom Pedro I in August 1821, but in 1972 this decree was censored by the Federal Police Department. Silenced in such a way that it could not even be mentioned, which shows the guidelines that censorship would follow: it would start from the authoritarian government to defend it and, in this way, defend itself (SOARES, 1989). Due to the damages caused by the censorship activity, whether partial or total, we affirm that the withdrawal of freedom of expression means the loss of a universal right that is freedom.

When studying documents produced by the repression agencies of the dictatorship and news published in the media of the period, we find discourses that associate mentions of free love and homosexuality in literary works, music, films and television programs, with the destruction of moral values of Brazilian society. . Insinuating that this was part of a subversive plan that jeopardized national security.

Therefore, it is worth explaining that the rise of the Bolsheviks to power in Russia after the October Revolution impacted the world, causing the growth of the influence of communist ideals in different parts (SETEMY, 2018). Between the Russian Revolution and the crisis of real socialism between the 1980s and 1990s, communism gained considerable power. The Cuban Revolution in 1959 threw South America into the center of the Cold War, influencing the pulverisation of parties and movements that cultivated followers, stimulating the action of communists. As a result, more conservative sectors of society, frightened, rushed to articulate a counteroffensive, anti-communism.

The idea that Brazil was at risk of being invaded and governed by communist ideology was the main justification for the overthrow of President João Goulart, in 1964. family, as well as the dismantling of the Church's influence in society. To this, Brito points out that there were indeed “theoretical elaborations and revolutionary experiences in Russia about free love, family, collectivization of domestic work” (BRITO, 2019, p.14), controversial propositions in the patriarchal Brazilian society.

In contrast to the conservative logics that were hidden behind the 64 coup, historian Douglas Marcelino (2006) writes that, in the 60s, there was a change in behavior hitherto considered daring or prohibited, which began to be discussed in the press, following the example of equality between the sexes. It was also during this period that the use of contraceptive pills became popular, signaling a great advance in what corresponds to female sexual freedom. Sandra Reimão (2015), however, argues that while several countries experienced profound changes in behavior, in Brazil the military regime proclaimed its retrograde values.

Indeed, it is observed that the fear of the nation disintegrating due to the entry of “exotic doctrines” shared by the military and civil society sectors that facilitated the coup (SETEMY, 2018), suited the preexisting tradition of country's censorship, as well as the conservative values ingrained in Brazilian society, which was resistant to the changes in behavior of the 60's of the last century.

In this sense, confirming that there was participation of civil sectors in support of the dictatorship and that, as defended by Darnton (2016, p. 279), “no system can operate based on mere coercion [...] Everyone needs true believers”. We brought two letters addressed to Armando Falcão, then Minister of Justice, which reflect the conservatism of the Brazilian population and express support for the censorship of Cassandra Rios. Below is a letter from Dr. Lacerda Nicoleti, director-president of the Hospital de Caridade São Roque do Morro da Fumaça, in Santa Catarina:

Most Honorable Sir:

We read in "Correio do Povo" the censorship that Your Excellency. applied to the book "O Eterno Sexo", by João Francisco de Lima. Forgive us for daring to come to Your Excellency. to start a few words, but we cannot fail to praise your attitude, in this troubled matter whose edges, which are too sharp, already exceed the beautiful acceptable by common sense, and whose vector result often requires the energetic interference of our representatives.

Severity is a virtue of the Gods, authority is a virtue of men, and both are of the Minister. It is necessary a wide action of censorship of the countless "João de Lima" spread throughout the country to produce nefarious, clumsy works, denigrating what our Brazil is capable of showing good for popular reading. Writers of this type, as well as Adelaide Carraro (Carniça is a scandalous book), Cassandra Rios, Brigitte Bijon and others, must be properly monitored so that they do not take advantage of

the innocence of the people through their writings that are especially harmful to our youth.

They create their books devoid of any educational, informative or messenger sense, and they are placed on newsstands with an ostensible banner "forbidden for minors under 21". It's intolerable. It's ridiculous. And the worst thing is that his works find a fertile cradle in the bosom of the popular mass in search of extravagant sensations and who are unable to assess the dangerousness that intoxicates his mind and clouds his spirit, nor to conjecture about the petty interests that they cover themselves in the putrefying licentiousness of people (authors) who do not go beyond exhaling the breath of their sick, annoying and vexing sexualities.

Sex was, is and will continue to be beautiful, as long as you control the means to your own end.

It was the greed of the gods, the victory of the saints, the light of poets, the furniture of wars, matter of the courts, and our common origin, but there are those who pervert it, who corrode and distort it, and throw its tentacles sharpened in a juvenile environment that should above all be protected and oriented in this sense.

[...]

We therefore express our vote of confidence, and our desire that by waving the auverde tassel, Your Excellency. know that our common-sense countrymen share Your Excellency. with the main purpose of healing an open wound in the literary structure of "Ultima Flor do Latio"

Our pale appeal for adequate supervision of literary productions and that your index point to a better future for our young people who read. (Source: Public Entertainment Censorship Division Fund. SIAN. National Archives. Document No.: br_dfanbsb_ns_agr_cof_msc_0071_d0001de0001).

It is noted, in the above fragment, the concern with what circulates in bookstores, with a focus on literature considered to be an attack on the morale of the population and that the mobilization of this type of arguments was not exclusive to members of the censorship, the military or government agents. (BRITO, 2019). By itself, the reading of the passage suggests a multiplicity of problematizations.

As we can read, the letter is immersed in a conservative tradition built in society, where the reading of erotic books is associated with the moral degradation of youth, as well as promiscuity. The Doctor. Lacerda argues that the books written by Rios are inadequate, based on a heteronormative worldview, since the moral dimension written in the letter is based on traditional notions of gender, family and honor. According to what Brito (2019, p. 08) writes, "political disputes were fought within military governments over the moral agenda". The letter reproduced above brings with it the association between sex with danger, with suspicion. Its author considers the questioning of social gender roles as corruption of customs.

Such prerogatives were related to the desire for a social order without antagonisms, fostering the relationship between politics and morals during the civil-military dictatorship. As it turns out, moral conservatism cannot be reduced to anti-communist propaganda employed by sectors of the government. On the contrary, they reflect a previous assumption, which is the maintenance of the configuration of gender roles, in which Cassandra Rios was harmful.

Regarding these concepts that refer to current discussions, it is worth remembering that the notion of history of the present time refers to an unstable notion of time, which grows on the uncertainty of the linearity of the past, present and future. Theorist François Dosse explains that the “history of the present time is at the intersection of the present and long duration. This poses the problem of knowing how the present is constructed in time” (DOSSE, 2012, p. 06). This allows us to reflect on the permanence of conjectures over time, such as the continuities of prejudices and negative discourses about sexualities that deviate from the heteronormative orbit and the reproduction of ideals of the past.

Gender roles and literary censorship

Over the last century, historiography has experienced an expansion of theoretical perspectives and interdisciplinary themes and, within this movement, themes that focus on aspects such as sexuality and gender are presented with relevance, affirming their places in History.

The preference for the use of the gender category instead of the sex category refers to the action of rejecting the imposition of biological determinism on what it would be like to “be a man” and “being a woman”. Since the sex category internalizes defined characteristics about the roles that men and women fulfill in society. Camila Gomes (2018, p. 68) writes that “gender would be a concept, a category of analysis” which tends to reinterpret the forms of knowledge and power that are imposed on us by the system in which we are inserted and is fundamental for a study that intends to be expansive. Going beyond the rigid male/female binarism, investing efforts against the essentialist logic that binarism determines, imposing its deconstruction. In this context, discussing the censorship of Cassandra Rios in the academy is to understand the political dimension of the gender category that causes a bifurcation between the public and private spheres.

Starting from the Christian and colonizing logic, the division between the sexes seems to be part of the order of things. The social world builds the body and from it the sexualizing division that defines what it is to be a man and what it is to be a woman in society. Sheltered in religious and medical discourses, homosexuality is seen as a transgression of order. In view of this, the definition of the organization of society by the opposition of the sexual organs is a product, as the French sociologist Bourdieu (2012, p. 23) writes, “of a construction carried out at the expense of a series of guided choices, or rather, by accentuating certain differences” or by excluding certain similarities.

With this focus, the divisions and binary combinations such as beautiful/ugly, good/bad, left/right, dominated/dominating help to situate the existence and the differences imbricated in the man/woman binarism in societies, as well as to show that the relationships human beings are permeated with social constructions.

In this way, when Dr. Lacerda Nicoleti writes to the minister saying that “writers of this type, as are Adelaide Carraro (Carniça is a scandalous book), Cassandra Rios, Brigitte Bijon and others, must undergo adequate surveillance” he is defending which roles the genres must fulfill and are being corrupted by the books of the aforementioned writers ⁵. Therefore, the fear is confirmed that the naturalization of deviant behaviors such as homosexuality and sexual freedom was part of a political dispute, fought not only at the heart of the government, but also by the population. From this perspective, conservatives have read the world and politicized sexuality, culminating in the moral agenda of the regime's defenders.

We also find in another letter also addressed to the Ministry of Justice, references to Cassandra Rios. This time the sender is Moacyr Coelho, identified as Director-General of the DPF, Federal Police, as we can read below:

Brasília, DF., November 6, 1975.

Minister:

I submit to Your Excellency's high consideration a copy of the book "COPACABANA POSTO 6" A MADRASTA, by Cassandra Rios, which, as it contains material that is offensive to morals and good customs, as the attached opinion emphasizes, is subject to the measure provided for in article 3 of Decree - Law No. 1077, of 1970.

2. At this time when the Government is committed to repressing, as it is urgent, the dissemination of literature that threatens to destroy the moral values of Brazilian society, it seems to me opportune and necessary that, in addition to the seizure of unreleased copies, the publishers are held criminally responsible, in accordance with the provisions of Article 5 of Decree-Law No. 1077, of 1970, the only way to contain the growing emergence of works of this genre.

3. This is what I have the honor to propose to Your Excellency, who will, however, deign to resolve as he deems most appropriate.

I take this opportunity to renew to Your Excellency my assurances of high esteem and distinguished consideration. (Source: Public Entertainment Censorship Division Fund. SIAN. National Archives. Document No.: br_dfanbsb_ns_agr_cof_cso_0579_d0001de0001).

In this excerpt, the sender mentions the 3rd article of Decree-Law 1.077/70, which provided for censorship of topics that violated morals and good customs

Art. 1º Publications and externalizations contrary to morals and good customs, whatever the means of communication, will not be tolerated;

⁵Adelaide Carraro (1936-1992) was a São Paulo writer also known for writing controversial novels about sexuality and politics. He died at the age of 55, a victim of cancer and with about 46 books published. According to Piovesan (2005), Carraro has a varied work, whose main theme is denunciation. His most relevant book was *Eu e o Governador*, from 1963, about a young woman with tuberculosis who gets involved with politicians to get a public job. He was referring to the governor of São Paulo and, at the time, President of the Republic, Jânio Quadros. Brigitte Bijou, in turn, was the pseudonym of the actor and writer Paulo Silvino (1939-2017) when he was dedicated to writing erotic books in the mid-1960s.

Art. 2. It will be up to the Ministry of Justice, through the Federal Police Department, to verify, when deemed necessary, before the publication of books and periodicals, the existence of material infringing the prohibition stated in the previous article.

Art. 3° Once verified the existence of material offensive to morals and good customs, the Minister of Justice will prohibit the publication of the publication and will determine the search and seizure of all its copies. (REIMÃO, 2011, p. 22-23).

About how censorship worked and how the aforementioned decree worked, some explanations are needed. According to historian Carlos Fico (2004), there was not a single censorship during the military dictatorship, but two: censorship of the press and censorship of public entertainment that affected plays, films and books. They distinguished themselves from each other and faced problems and contradictions. On the one hand, the ban on the press accompanied the height of repression that, for Fico, took place between the late 1960s and early 1970s, while censorship of public entertainment reached its peak when a certain “opening” of the regime in the late 1970s. However, it appears that the essence of both originates in the “long Brazilian tradition of authoritarian thinking” (FICO, 2004, p. 38), which predates the military dictatorship.

In line with this, historian Sandra Reimão points out that there was a growth in the publishing market in the 1970s, as a result of the fall in the illiteracy rate and the increase in the number of university students in the country. According to her, the censorship of culture between the 60s and 70s was articulated in two ways, sometimes correlated and often integrated: in the fight against subversive propaganda and in the fight against works that undermined morals and good customs (REIMÃO, 2015).). It can be seen, then, that the two letters we read were written in this period, in 1976 and 1975, respectively.

Namely, the letters were addressed to the Minister of Justice Armando Falcão, which, according to Marcelino (2006), was the period in which more publications were censored for moral reasons. The historian Carlos Fico confirms this assertion, because for him. it was during Falcão's administration that the workload of the censors was greatest and they examined everything from dress rehearsals to trailers and synopses of soap opera chapters in search, above all, of pornography. Thus, “books considered pornographic were incinerated at the Municipal Urban Cleaning Company of Rio de Janeiro” (FICO, 2002, p. 266).

In this sense, Reimão considers that it was at the end of the regime that censorship was more committed to working and raises three hypotheses to justify this difference: the first would be that the censorship of public entertainment would have a more “moralistic” intention than the press censorship. and therefore complied with these criteria. The second hypothesis revolves around the assumption that, when perceiving the weakening of the regime, the more committed it was to show its workforce, showing itself as necessary to the system and to society.

The third possible justification, finally, is that during the so-called “years of lead”, artists, writers and intellectuals were aware of the rigor of the censorship activity that was carried out during the Medici government and carried out a “self-censorship”, in order to avoid produce something that could be censored. After all, the country was ruled by the so-called “hard line” military (REIMÃO, 2011) and the consequences would entail financial losses, given the ban on ready-made material.

Armando Falcão was Alfredo Buzaid's successor in the Ministry of Justice during the Ernesto Geisel government (1974-1979) and became known as the “guardian of morals and good customs”. As a minister, he had received many letters guaranteeing support, collaboration and demanding greater rigor in censorship, as shown by the letters attached here. In them, there is an “attempt to use a 'public good' (censorship) to resolve a case in the private sphere (such as the ethical and moral education of children)” (MARCELINO, 2006, p. 209). It appears that people, in the correspondence, assimilate the population as naive, incapable of orienting themselves about what should be read or not, with the need for guardianship by the authorities, such as the appeal to ban the work *Copacabana Posto 6 - A stepmother* (1969).

By the way, this book exemplifies the censorship of Rios well. In it, the author writes “stories of non-marital and non-heterosexual sex” (PIOVEZAN; FONTOURA JUNIOR, 2015, p. 2415) and, it was understood, her readers without discernment would act according to what was published, in family breakdown and promiscuity. Resulting in a destabilized nation.

So, under the stigma of a pervert, Cassandra Rios went against the grain of the “ideal nation”, where anything that was a threat to order would not fit. In the novel, in which the author of the above letter asks for greater attention from the authorities, the author wrote the story of Laura, who is experiencing a conflict due to her “homosexual condition” (MANTOVANI, 2019, p. 07).

Laura is a 26-year-old girl, described as a misfit, with conflicting family relationships. She and her brother Sidney were raised by Aunt Mafalda, after the death of their mother, whom Laura treats with contempt. In the plot, Rios exposes a family unbalanced by the death of the mother and the absence of the widowed father, who goes to Europe after the loss of his wife, leaving his children in the care of his sister-in-law, imagining that keeping them in a high standard of living would be enough to make up for its absence.

The father's return to Brazil is the major turning point in the narrative, causing misunderstandings between Laura and her father. It is latent his non-acceptance of the new wife, Jeanne- Marie, portrayed as much younger than her father, with whom the protagonist

Laura ends up having a crush. Tia Mafalda also leaves the place before the arrival of Egberto and his wife, claiming that she has already done her part in educating her nephews.

At its climax, it is revealed that Laura's biological mother is actually Aunt Mafalda. Faced with this discovery, the protagonist stands against her father. At one point, the author delivers a conversation full of accusations and, as she leaves her father's office where the argument was taking place, Laura finds Jeanne-Marie and takes her for a ride. Laura accelerates the car while questioning Jeanne-Marie about what the two experienced the other night. And between exchanges of declarations of love, the car flips over and falls overboard. The end of the book brings the tragic death of the two.

In the dialogues of the plot, Rios points out some propositions that, in some way, show the marginalized reality that the gay and lesbian population lived in the period, as well as what the family expected from Laura as a woman:

At home, he had already had countless proofs that his brother was more well-liked, more esteemed. For what reasons? Because of her behavior and, more than anything, because of her type. How guilty would it be if nature had made her like that, thin, masculine, different, after all! By what right then did they not allow her to live as she wished? They were always admonishing her, criticizing her, promoting fights where they couldn't bend her or make her a girl with a narrow and delicate waist. (RIOS, 1969, p. 17. *Apud* . MANTOVANI, 2019, p. 07).

Thus, in a period in which lesbian visibility was almost nil, identifying and coming out as a lesbian was living with a permanent feeling of unimportance. Groping through these documents opens us to current reflections, such as the extent to which the marginality of the LGBTQIA+ minority has been overcome. The emergence of this study reveals that the State of exception had motivations beyond the disputes of the economic models of the Cold War, dictatorships in Latin America were also marked by moralizing and conservative discourses ⁶. It can be seen, then, that compulsory heterosexuality, which structures the patriarchal society, condemns people to exclusion and silencing.

Final considerations

In addition to writing lesbian and erotic novels, the featured author transcribed a context of police repression and persecution of her sexuality considered deviant — in which censorship, politics and the sex/gender paradigm present fine lines and acquire strength through the operation of a purposefully defined speech. Therefore, investigating gender relations is an

⁶Recent research makes it possible to sustain that the dictatorships in the Southern Cone were also marked by gender and sexuality, as in the work of Débora D'antônio, *Deseo y represión: sexualidad, género y Estado en la historia argentina reciente* (2016), on the dictatorship Argentina and the doctoral thesis by Enrique Padros on the dictatorship in Uruguay, entitled *Como el Uruguay no hay... State Terror and National Security* (2005).

interdisciplinary action that deserves attention from the academy because it is inherently related to human relations and political actions as a whole. The relevance of this research, in the light of the History of the Present Time, is revealed as the repressions of the past are used to justify the same prejudices of today, and, therefore, lack careful review, respecting the sensitivity of the sources.

It should be noted that stereotypes in the image of the LGBTQIA + population in Brazil were not created and personified in the context of the military dictatorship, but rather are prior to that, nor are episodes of violence and censorship restricted to the past. Attacks on this minority are common in the news, such as the comic that was censored by the former mayor of Rio de Janeiro Marcelo Crivella (Republicans) at the XIX International Book Biennial in September 2019 (KER, 2019); in the speech of the current president of the Republic, Jair Bolsonaro (without a party), who said "Now I'm a boy like Maranhão, is that it?" when trying a pink soda in Maranhão on his first visit to the state (BOLSONARO..., 2020).

In short, this topic and the various discussions arising from it regarding gender are not exhausted. Reminiscences and continuities of the repression of female sexuality and the dictatorial period in its various aspects are still sensitive. What is up to us to reflect on such facts from the perspective of the History of the Present Time.

As we have already mentioned, the theorist Dosse (2012, p. 06) writes that "the history of the present time is at the intersection of the present and the long duration". By handling it, the historian expands his horizon and finds a present whose transparency implies a new historical consciousness, a new historiographical conception. After all, "the present is no longer seen in our time as a simple place of continuous passage between a before and after, but as a gap between the past and the future" (DOSSE, 2012, p. 20).

Thus, the letters against Cassandra Rios show conservative justifications that found support in a political discourse based on precepts prior to the military regime, while Odete's writing asserted itself as resistance and meant support for her readers and for lesbian subjectivity. Finally, to study it is to resist, once again, against the conservatism of some sectors of the Brazilian population that still defends the marginality of the LGBTQIA + community.

SOURCES

Document br_dfanbsb_ns_agr_cof_msc_0071_d0001de0001. Public Entertainment Censorship Fund, SIAN, National Archives.

Document br_dfanbsb_ns_agr_cof_cso_0579_d0001de0001. Public Entertainment Censorship Fund, SIAN, National Archives.

REFERENCES

BOLSONARO MAKES A homophobic joke after drinking pink soda in Maranhão. *Free Turnstile* , São Paulo, 29 Oct. 2020. Available at: [https://catracalivre.com.br/cidadania/bolsonaro-faz-piada-homofobica-apos-beber-refrigerante-rosa-no-maranha o/](https://catracalivre.com.br/cidadania/bolsonaro-faz-piada-homofobica-apos-beber-refrigerante-rosa-no-maranha-o/). Accessed on: 11/14/2020.

BOURDIEU, Pierre. *Male domination* . 11 ed. Rio de Janeiro: Bertrand Brazil, 2012.

BRAZIL. National Truth Commission. *Report* : thematic texts. Brasília: CNV, 2014. v. two.

BRITO, Antônio MF Subversion by sex: anti-communist representations during the dictatorship in Brazil. *Varies History* , Belo Horizonte, v. 36, no. 72, Sep-Dec 2020, p. 859-888.

BRITO, Antônio MF “A true bacchanal, a stupid thing”: anti-communism, sexuality and youth in the time of the dictatorship. *90's* , Porto Alegre, v. 26, 2019, p. 1-22.

CORTECERTU, Jair dos Santos. Cassandra Rios defied censorship to become the first Brazilian to sell 1 million books and educate a generation. *Folha de São Paulo* , São Paulo, 8 Mar. 2018. Available at: <http://acervofolha.blogfolha.uol.com.br/2018/03/08/cassandra-rios-desafiou-censura-para-se-tornar-a-primeira-brasileira-a-vender-1-million-of-books-and-educating-a-generation/>. Accessed on: 7 Apr. 2018

DARNTON, Robert. *Censors in Action* : How States Influenced Literature. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras, 2016.

DOSSE, Francois. History of the Present Time and Historiography. *Tempo e Argumento Magazine* , Florianópolis, v. 4, no. 1, 2012, p. 05-22.

FACCHINI, Regina; FRANÇA, Isadora L. Of colors and hues: subjects, connections and challenges in the Brazilian LGBT movement. *Sexualidad, Salud y Sociedad* , Rio de Janeiro, n. 3, 2009, p. 54-81.

FICO, Carlos. History of the Present Time, traumatic events and sensitive documents - the Brazilian case. *Varies History* , Belo Horizonte, v. 28, no. 47, jan-jun 2012, p. 43-59.

FICO, Carlos. *How they acted* : the underground of the military dictatorship. Rio de Janeiro: Record, 2001.

FICO, Carlos. “Dear censorship”: letters to the military regime. *Topoi* , Rio de Janeiro, v. 3, no. 5, Jul./Dec. 2002, p. 251-286.

FICO, Carlos. Versions and controversies about 1964 and the military dictatorship. *Brazilian Journal of History* , São Paulo, v. 24, no. 47, 2004, p. 29-64.

GOMES, Camilla de M. Gender as a category of decolonial analysis. *Civitas-Revista de Ciências Sociais* , Porto Alegre, vol. 18, No. 1, Jan-Apr 2018, p. 65-82.

KER, John. Censorship against LGBTs goes far beyond Crivela and the Bienal. *Hybrid Magazine* . 09 sep. 2019. Available at: <https://revistahibrida.com.br/2019/09/09/a-censura-contra-lgbts-esta-muito-alem-de-crivella-e-da-bienal/> . Accessed on: 11/14/2020.

MARCELINO, Douglas A. *Saving the homeland from pornography and subversion : the censorship of books and public entertainment in the 1970s*. Dissertation (Master in History), Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro, 2006.

MCMAHON, Robert J. *Cold War* . Porto Alegre: L&PM, 2012.

MANTOVANI, Flavia. Subversive Cassandra Rios? An analysis of sexuality in Copacabana Posto 6. *ANPUH-PE* , 2019, p. 1-11.

IN THE 70's, no one was censored more than Cassandra Rios. *O Globo* , Rio de Janeiro, 18 Oct. 2013. Available at : <http://acervo.oglobo.globo.com/em-destaque/nos-anos-70-ninguem-foi-mais-censurado-no-brasil-do-que-cassandra-rios-10425009#ixzz51a2NByBu> . Accessed on: 16 Dec. 2017.

ORIANI, Angélica P. First drafts: approximations between Michel de Certeau and the History of the Present Time. *Tempo e Argumento Magazine* , Florianópolis, v. 9, n.22, Sep-Dec 2017, p. 316-338.

PIOVESAN, Adriane. *Romantic love x delight of the senses : Cassandra Rios and the female homoerotic identity in literature (1948-1942)*. Dissertation (Master in Letters), Federal University of Paraná, Paraná, 2005.

PIOVEZAN, Adriane; FONTOURA JUNIOR, Antonio. Censored bodies: moralism in the period of the civil-military dictatorship and the literature of Cassandra Rios. *VII INTERNATIONAL HISTORY CONGRESS* , 2015, p. 2407-2417.

PICCOLO, Monica; SULIDADE, Mariana da. *Republican Maranhão in focus : State, press and historiography*. São Luís, Publisher Shalom/EDUEMA, 2015.

PADROS, Enrique S. History of the Present Time, National Security Dictatorships and Repressive Archives. *Tempo e Argumento Magazine* , Florianópolis, v. 1, no. 1, jan-jun 2009, p. 30-45.

REIMON, Sandra. Cassandra Rios - on the wrong side of the road. Communication, culture and social media - *XIV Ibercom* , São Paulo, vol. 14, 2015, p. 7346-7352.

REIMÃO, Sandra LAA *Repression and resistance : censorship of books in the military dictatorship*. Thesis (Free Teaching in Communication and Culture), University of São Paulo, São Paulo, 2011.

SANTOS, Rick. Cassandra Rios and the emergence of gay and lesbian literature in Brazil. *Gender Magazine* , Niterói, v. 4, no. 1, 2003, p. 17-31.

SETEMY, Adriana CL Vigilantes of morals and good customs: social and cultural conditions for the political structuring of censorship during the military dictatorship. *Topoi* , Rio de Janeiro, v. 19. n. 37, Jan-Apr 2018, p. 171-197.

SOARES, Gláucio AD Censorship during the authoritarian regime. *Brazilian Journal of Social Sciences* , São Paulo, v. 4, no. 10, Jun. 1989, p. 21-43.